

Long term leaching studies on Coal Combustion Residues from Balco Captive Power Plant, Korba

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Abstract : The study was conducted to assess the leaching of coal combustion residues (CCRs) from Balco Captive Power Plant, Korba, India through five different standard techniques. The leaching procedures included acid digestion, short term (24-hour shake test, TCLP) and long term leaching (Open column percolation experiments, ASTM column experiments) studies for a period of more than three years. The physico-chemical characteristics (pH, conductivity and TDS) were observed within the permissible limits. The leachates were analysed for twenty-three elements like Na, K, Mg, Ca, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Pb, Mn, Cr, Co, Cd, Se, Al, Ag, As, B, Ba, V, Sb, Mo, W and compared with their compositional analysis. Among these elements, only Na, K, Mg and Ca were found to be leaching throughout the study period and were within permissible limits of the prescribed standards (IS : 2490). However, Fe, Pb, Ni, Cu and Mn were observed at significant concentration levels on a few occasions. Overall, this study establishes the CCRs of Balco Captive Power Plant as environmentally benign material and encourages its large-scale utilisation.

Keywords : Coal Combustion Residues, trace elements, leaching.

Introduction

The most common practice to dispose off Coal Combustion Residues (CCRs) is by piling them at disposal sites called as ash ponds by means of hydraulic transportation¹. CCRs come in contact with water during transport and disposal phases due to rain or within the ash ponds during storage. This equilibrium with water may lead to the leaching of trace elements within ash ponds which may result in contamination of both ground and surface water²⁻⁸.

Assessment of long-term environmental status of CCRs

in terms of leaching is indispensable to determine the possible avenues of utilization⁹⁻¹¹. Hence, it is essential to determine their leaching potential in terms of toxicity in presence of different leaching mediums for an extended duration of time. The objective of this paper is to establish the true environmental status of CCRs from Balco Captive Power Plant through leaching and assess the possibility of utilization.

Results and discussion

Tables 1(a) and (b) present the compositional analysis of CCRs. It shows that the CCRs are primarily composed

Table 1(a). Summary of compositional analysis (%) of CCRs

Samples	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	TiO ₂
FA	55.61	30.25	7.69	5.12	2.16	3.15	2.68	1.45	1.82
BA	56.23	29.82	6.54	5.42	1.75	2.45	1.56	0.58	0.34
PA	42.28	21.35	4.51	3.26	0.42	0.38	0.27	0.39	0.21

Table 1(b). Summary of qualitative analysis of CCRs

Samples	Major elements	Minor elements	Traces
FA	Si, Al, Fe, Na, K, Ca, Mg	S, Ti	Zn, Cu, Ni, Mn, Cr, Pb, P
BA	Si, Al, Fe, Na, Ca	K, Ca, Mg, S, Ti	Zn, Cu, Ni, Mn, Cr, Pb, P
PA	Si, Al, Fe, Na	K, Ca, Mg, S, Ti	Zn, Cu, Ni, Mn, Cr, Pb, P

of oxides of silicon, aluminium, iron, sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, sulphur and titanium. It also contains traces (<0.2 ppm) of zinc, copper, nickel, manganese, chromium, lead and phosphorus. The extent of leaching of surfacial elements is reflected through various types of leaching procedures. The leachates were neutral to slightly alkaline in nature. Electrical conductivity indicates the different availability of ions in CCRs and is related to the Total Dissolved Solids. Conductivity of the samples also showed decreasing trend which can be correlated with elemental concentration. Irregular patterns in concentration levels may be attributed to a number of interactions like association/disruption/dissolution etc. taking place within them.

Acid Digest data (Table 2a) showed the concentration at elevated levels compared to the other tests due to leaching of inert materials under influence of strong acids as total elemental concentration. Thus, they do not repre-

sent the true leaching behaviour. 24 h shake test (Table 2b) resulted in significantly lower concentration levels compared to the other tests. Most of the parameters were within the permissible limits. Cobalt, cadmium, selenium, aluminum, silver, arsenic, boron, barium, vanadium, antimony, molybdenum and mercury did not show any leaching at all.

TCLP leachate data (Table 3a) gave comparatively higher levels due to slightly acidic-buffered conditions. It represents the accelerated leaching because of 1 : 20 solid to liquid (leachant) ratio. Chromium, nickel cobalt, cadmium, selenium, aluminum, silver, arsenic, boron, barium, vanadium, antimony, molybdenum and mercury were reported below the detection limit during the entire study period. ASTM column leaching (Table 3b) showed the results to be in agreement with the open column percolation studies. Sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, manganese, copper, iron, zinc and lead were observed in

Table 2(a). Summary of leachate analysis (a) acid digest test and (b) 24-hour shake test of samples

Parameters	FA	BA	PA	(IS : 2490, 1981)	
				Inland surface water	On land for irrigation
Sodium	34	22	10.5	-	60
Potassium	31	25	16	-	-
Calcium	2.25	1.80	0.48	-	-
Magnesium	2.86	2.45	1.205	-	-
Manganese	0.065	0.042	0.022	-	-
Copper	0.042	0.035	0.018	3	-
Iron	7.86	8.45	12.68	-	-
Zinc	0.035	0.032	0.025	5	-
Lead	0.086	0.05	0.32	0.1	-
Chromium	0.035	BDL	BDL	2	-

Table 2(b)

pH	7.27	8.65	7.52	5.5-9.0	5.5-9.0
Conductivity	0.076	0.043	0.032	-	-
TDS	35	20	22	2100	-
Sodium	20	11	14	-	60
Potassium	16	10	7	-	-
Calcium	4.12	3.42	3.78	-	-
Magnesium	3.82	2.25	3.50	-	-
Manganese	0.018	BDL	BDL	-	-
Copper	0.056	0.032	0.014	3	-
Iron	1.389	0.686	0.587	-	-
Zinc	0.016	BDL	BDL	5	-
Lead	0.017	0.012	BDL	0.1	-

BDL : Below detectable limit; conc. of elements in mg/L; TDS in ppm; conductivity in mmhos/cm.

Table 3(a). Summary of leachate analysis (a) TCLP test and (b) ASTM column of samples

Parameters	FA	BA	PA	(IS : 2490, 1981)	
				Inland surface water	On land for irrigation
pH	5.12	5.48	5.25	5.5-9.0	5.5-9.0
Conductivity	3.362	2.25	3.50	-	-
TDS	23	17	9	2100	-
Sodium	46	38	25	-	60
Potassium	22	15	16	-	-
Calcium	40	28	31	-	-
Magnesium	2.45	1.76	1.25	-	-
Manganese	0.012	BDL	BDL	-	-
Copper	0.031	0.021	0.176	3	-
Iron	0.028	0.016	0.015	-	-
Zinc	0.022	BDL	BDL	5	-
Lead	0.242	0.125	BDL	0.1	-

Table 3(b)

pH	5.69	6.12	7.28	5.5-9.0	5.5-9.0
Conductivity	0.225	0.268	0.315	-	-
TDS	121	125	136	2100	-
Sodium	39	36	21	-	60
Potassium	30	21	19	-	-
Calcium	68	38	29	-	-
Magnesium	29	22	19	-	-
Manganese	0.023	BDL	0.012	-	-
Copper	BDL	0.019	BDL	3	-
Iron	0.215	0.129	0.056	-	-
Zinc	0.23	0.123	BDL	5	-
Lead	0.012	BDL	BDL	0.1	-

the leachates. Chromium, nickel, cobalt, cadmium, selenium, aluminum, silver, arsenic, boron, barium, vanadium, antimony, molybdenum and mercury were reported below the detection limit during the entire study period.

Open column percolation studies (Table 4) showed the presence of sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, manganese, copper, iron, zinc and lead in the leachates. Chromium, cobalt, cadmium, selenium, aluminum, silver, arsenic, boron, barium, vanadium, tin, molybdenum and tungsten could not be detected (< 0.001 mg/L) through any of the methodologies during the entire study period. Calcium, magnesium, sodium and potassium showed regular leaching and were found to be leaching during the entire course of study. Manganese, copper, iron, zinc and lead showed intermittent leaching. Leaching showed decreasing trend with time. For instance, the variation of pH of leachates with time is shown in Fig. 1. The initial

high concentrations may be attributed to the early dissolution of easily exchangeable elements called as 'first flush' followed by a slow release of the elements afterwards. Accordingly, the pond ash samples showed lower of elemental concentrations compared to the fly ash and bottom ash samples.

Experimental

CCRs [Fly ash (FA), Bottom ash (BA) and Pond ash (PA)] were and homogenized to result representative samples. Short-term leaching (shake) tests, ASTM column and long term leaching (Open column percolation) experiments^{12,13} were carried as briefly described below :

Acid digestion : 0.5 g of the oven-dried sample was moistened by 2 ml of perchloric acid. To it 10 ml of conc. HNO_3 was added and heated to dryness. Thereafter

Table 4. Summary of the leachate analysis (Open column percolation experiment) of CCR samples

Parameters	FA	BA	PA	(IS : 2490, 1981)	
				Inland surface water	On land for irrigation
pH	4.98–9.92	6–9.05	5.86–9	5.5–9.0	5.5–9.0
Conductivity	0.098–0.962	0.012–0.825	0.085–0.945	–	–
TDS	55–485	35–400	48–568	2100	–
Sodium	2–51	1–45	1–48	–	60
Potassium	2–47	1–40	1–51	–	–
Calcium	1–79	1–45	1–67	–	–
Magnesium	1–98	1–61	1–38	–	–
Manganese	BDL – 0.092	BDL – 0.064	BDL – 0.210	–	–
Copper	BDL – 0.240	BDL – 0.290	BDL – 0.046	3	–
Iron	BDL – 3.120	BDL – 3.147	BDL – 4.523	–	–
Zinc	BDL – 0.965	BDL – 0.586	BDL – 0.492	5	–
Lead	BDL – 0.48	BDL – 0.32	BDL – 0.064	0.1	–

BDL : Below detectable limit; conc. of elements in mg/L; TDS in ppm; conductivity in mmhos/cm.

it was digested for 3–4 h after adding 20 ml of 10% HNO_3 . It was filtered, made up to 100 ml and kept for analysis.

24 h Shake test (ASTM D 398) : Two litre of distilled water was added to 80 g of CCR sample and closed tightly in an extraction bottle. This was followed by an end-on-end rotation at 30 rpm for 24 h.

Toxicity characteristic leachate procedure (EPA1311) : 5 g of sample was taken and then extraction fluid equal to twenty times the amount of sample was added in a zero head extractor under pressure. The system placed in an end-over-end rotary agitator for 18 h, at 30 ± 2 rpm at a room temperature. The extract was filtered using 0.7 micron pore size filter paper and kept for analysis.

ASTM column : One pore volume of distilled water was forced through the packed columns of CCRs each day in a saturated up flow mode. The rate of percolation was controlled by applying variable nitrogen pressure. The column packing was determined by ASTM standards.

Open percolation column experiments : Deionised water was percolated through a column packed with the specific type of CCR according to the natural permeability of the material. The columns were 10 cm in diameter and 60 cm in length. The column set up involved packing the ash content as determined by Proctor Test. (Annual Book of ASTM Standards 11[10], 1990). The top 7.5 cm of the column was left unpacked to allow for the addition and maintenance of the leaching medium. About 200 ml of deionized water was added to the top of column once

every alternate day and the leachate was collected from the end hole.

Leachate analysis :

Potentiometric analysis : pH, conductivity and TDS of the leachates were measured potentiometrically by Century Water Analyser (CK-710).

Elemental analysis : The leachate samples were filtered and acidified using 2 ml conc. HNO_3 and preserved by chilling them. Sodium and potassium were determined using Systronics Flame Photometer. Concentration levels of trace elements were analysed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS GBC-902). Merck-AAS standards were used for standardization and calibration of AAS. Optimized operating conditions such as lamp current, wavelength, slit width, sensitivity, flame type for a particular element were used as specified in the manual.

Fig. 1. Open column leachate analysis for pH.

Conclusion :

(i) The leaching characteristics of the fly ash, bottom ash and pond ash were investigated. These compositions were found to overlap owing to origin from same quality of coal.

(ii) Shake tests exhibit elevated elemental concentrations due to acidic medium and vigorous shaking conditions. Thus, they do not represent the actual leaching conditions and emphasize the need to carry out leaching for extended duration of time. ASTM column experiments and Open percolation column experiments show the long term leaching behaviour and establish the CCRs to be non-toxic in nature.

(iii) Thirteen elements namely chromium, cobalt, cadmium, selenium, aluminum, silver, arsenic, boron, barium, vanadium, tin, molybdenum and tungsten did not show any leaching during the entire study period. The results show that leaching of trace/heavy elements were well within permissible limits as per IS : 2490 and also as per IS : 10500. Initial high concentration of heavy metals may be attributed to surfacial enrichment which decreased at a later stage due to first flush phenomenon.

(iv) The coal combustion residues were found to present no significant damage to the environment and may definitely be considered for bulk utilization for mine back filling or soil amendment for good vegetation.

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